

An Empirical Analysis of Component Based Software Development and Critical Evaluation of Component Selection using TOPSIS: A Quantitative Approach

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Abstract— The Component Based Software Development (CBSE) is an intrinsic part of Software Engineering developing the software systems with integration of reusable components. These components are collected from Commercial of the Shelf (COTS), which are developed by third parties. Component based construction reduces time, cost and human efforts for software development. The requirement engineer plays vital role in examining and selecting suitable components from COTS on multiple criteria of characteristics. TOPSIS is a quantitative approach, which solves such complex Multi Criteria Decision making problems effectively. This paper is to evaluate and choose the proper component from COTS using TOPSIS, which motivates the stakeholder satisfaction, reduces ambiguity, and prevents the software failure.

Keywords—TOPSIS, component selection, decision making, Integration, Component software Development.

I. INTRODUCTION

Software Industry is more dynamic industry compares with other industries which made the world as digital. Now it is nucleus for other industries. Software Engineering is a systematic, well defined and measureable approach for developing the software products within cost, time and with more quality. Lack of quality leads to customer dissatisfaction, with more budget, time and human efforts to the developer and firm image is also damaged. The faulty software systems can't fulfill functional, non-functional and domain requirements of various perspectives of end user. The other industries using reusable components such as electronic components on circuit board, vehicle parts replaced by components manufactured by different manufacturers. Roger.S.Pressman, 1977 expressed in his words as, "Today software industry is also moving towards component-based construction, even though most of software is to be custom built". Such as combo boxes, radio buttons, scrollbars, push buttons and check boxes etc. Component based software development in many application domains such as desktop graphical and web based application. These reusable components are developed by third parties which are available at commercially of the shelf(COTS)[8] for general public. The component quality is also assured for construction of software intensive system.

The pool of COTS consists variety of components related with Office documentation, Chemical Analysis, statistical and Accounting Packages. Components facilitate wide range of features to fit into the needs of versatile customer demands. The components are service providers in abstracted form in Object Oriented Systems[6]. The philosophy of Component Based Software Engineering (CBSE) states that "buy and don't build", which reduces the time, budget and human efforts .

The component domain engineering is to find suitable functional, behavioral and data components from stored Capability Knowledge Base. The Component Software Development consists various framework activities such as Analysis, construction, and dissemination of components. More efforts required for proper component selection, verification and its integration. The selection of suitable component from COTS is critical task and plays vital role in component based software development. Component selection depends on multiple evaluation criteria's, complexity may arise in selecting proper component, because criteria's may be in conflict with each other.

The Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution(TOPSIS) is a Multi-Criteria Decision Making system proposed to solve complex component selection problem. The selection of proper component from COTS can remove the ambiguity, misunderstanding, customer and dissatisfaction and prevents software failure. The rest of paper is as follows. The Section 2 illustrates Component Based Software Engineering and TOPSIS methodology literature. The Section 3 describes the overview spectrum of various phases in Component based software development. Section 4 states the mathematical representation of TOPSIS. The Section 5 describes component selection and Prioritization using TOPSIS. Finally a discussion of future directions and inferences is presented in section 6.

II. RELATED WORK

In recent a huge number of researchers highlighted various key points in component based software development. Many researchers worked on TOPSIS method for decision making in different domains of life discussed in literature. Their efforts are

useful to extend the knowledge for components selection using Quantitative Approach and proper implementation of effective approach used at right time motivates expected quality outcomes in software development.

- Bhupender Yadav and Anshu Yadav, published research paper on various testing techniques and its complexities in Component Based Software Development. They highlighted the role of testing in quality component based software artifacts[1].
- Isthia Verma elaborated design, construction and component applicability of component based construction with its limitations, advantages and disadvantages [2].
- Ivica Cmkovic, stig Larson and Michel Chaudron analyzed various steps involved in Component Based Software Development Life Cycle with a case study.
- Javed Ali Khan, Izaz Ur Rehman, Yawar Hayt Khan, Iftikhar and Salman Rashid[4] published a research paper on various techniques of requirement prioritization and proposed effective requirement prioritization technique which is fault tolerant.
- Javed Ali Khan [5] expressed that, Analytic Network Prioritization is a effective method among the seven methods with case study
- Karambir Singh and P.K. Suri[6], identified object oriented system properties in component based software products.
- R.M.Zulqarnain, M.Saeed,N.Ahmad, F.Dayan, B.Ahmad analyzed TOSIS method with case study of automotive vehicles [7].
- Sharanjit Singh, Amardeept Singh, Samson, Sandeep Singh emphasized interface binding, risks and complexities of component based software development. They proposed RAM process model for risk reduction in component based construction[8].
- Suryani Ismail, Wan M.N.Kadir [9], characterized component reusability of component based software. They conducted survey on software reuse at University of Malaysia. The findings or the metrics used to quantify reusable component.

III. COMPONENT BASED SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT AND ITS VARIOUS PHASES

The reusability extends limits of Software Engineering in Component software development [6]. This approach includes inheritance in Frame-Based Systems, and imports software nuggets from several areas of Artificial Intelligence such as Compositional Modeling and Ontological Engineering. The domain engineering selects proper functional, behavioral and data components from reuse libraries. These components are developed for open market, that will be used with different situations and configurations, many of them not known at the time of development[8]. The developers promote the components as black boxes with glue code [3].

Domain Engineering includes Analysis, Construction and Dissemination of components for existing and future purpose. Component Based software construction includes various activities such as identification, verification and forming the relations between components for developing final system. Locating and selecting proper component from the COTS is time consuming process than its integration in software development.

The Component Based Software Development starts with requirement specification, continues with selecting suitable component by evaluation and concludes with integration into final system. There is a need of proper component selection and evaluation before integration into the system[3].

The Component Based Software Development consists various phases such as:

Requirement Analysis and specification: Requirement Analysis is a primitive phase of Component Based Software Engineering same as conventional development. Requirement Engineer can analyze, negotiate the components which fulfill the requirements available in COTS, otherwise the risk to be incorporated.

Software Design: Specification and design are interrelated with availability of components. Components are specific, adhere with flexible component based model and architectural framework. Even though, it is complex to achieve interoperability with different architecture. The heterogeneous architectural decisions motivate the incompatibility and integration complexity. The Design tightly coupled together with its components [3]. Selection of proper components flexible with architectural design may be hard to find, software gaps may exist between features of components. There is a criticality in component selection which depends on many criteria's and alternatives. The component selection performed with formal selection method "Six Sigma" and informal methods like Experience-Based, Hands on-Trial Based and Customer Recommendation Based selection. The design usually needs more iteration for final outcome. Finally, the components are selected based on criteria, to build the application and new components are added and to be modified to achieve interoperability.

Fig. 1. Component Based Software Development

Implementation and Unit Testing: Components are coupled, unit testing and debugging is made as a part of implementation. Component glue-code which provides interface to integrate with other components for implementation of new functions. The integration testing is more crucial to achieve the interoperability than isolated testing of components.

System integration: Component Integration leads to deployment of final system. System integration is testing the system as whole. The verification and validation is little bit complex in component based software development due to glue code. The malfunction raises on another component if components are not properly integrated. Component interface plays vital role for system integration.

System Evaluation: Software system is not satisfies stakeholder overall time in business environment due to change of organization process and technology[1]. Definitely it needs regular maintenance according to client needs. In most of the cases the existing components are to be minimum modify, otherwise enhance with new components to the existing system.

IV MATHEMATICAL REPRESENTATION OF TOPSIS.

Software Component selection is a critical decision making composed with multiple criteria's and alternatives. One criteria contrast with another so there might be no way out satisfying all criteria simultaneously. There are numerous methods to solve MCDM problems. One of the method called TOPSIS presented by presented by Hwang and Yoon. The method has ability to solve wide area of real world problems ranging from banking, manufacturing, energy planning and the solutions are both objective and subjective. The TOPSIS solves various critical problems and derive solutions in more effective.

The TOPSIS is a popular Multi-Criteria Decision Making model invented by Hwang and Yoon in 1981. Chen and Hwang extend the idea of the TOPIS with a new model.

Zulqarnain developed graphical model of TOPSIS and implemented in medical field for diagnosis of disease. He used the trapezoidal fuzzy numbers by Sanchez's method for disease identification. TOPSIS extended by Chen for Group Decision Making in fuzzy atmosphere to solve uncertain data. Mahmoodzadeh developed technique combining fuzzy AHP and TOPSIS method.

Hwang and Yoon invented a method to solve MCDM know as the TOPSIS. It supports shortest Euclidean distance, proposed positive ideal solution(PIS) and negative ideal solution(NIS) and each criteria needs to be maximized or minimized. TOPSIS chooses the alternative of minimum Euclidean distance from ideal solution and derives maximum distance from negative ideal solution.

Steps involved in the TOPSIS method is as follows.

1. **Establish decision matrix (Evaluation matrix)** consisting of **M** alternatives and **N** criteria

$$(a_{ij})_{M \times N} \dots\dots\dots(4.1.1)$$

Example: Number of Components represented as **M** and Number of characteristics (Functionality, Usability, Interoperability and Cost) represented with **N**

2. Calculation of Normalized decision matrix (NDM):

$$\alpha_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^M (\alpha_{ij})^2}} \quad \dots \dots \dots (4.2.1)$$

(Each characteristics **j** for each component, **i** is normalized to be in between 0 and 1. The highest value is the better metric.)

3. Derivation of Weighted Normalized Decision Matrix[WNDM] .

It is essential to note that, each criteria of component have its own weight or significance, the sum weights equal to 1. The weights to be assessed randomly based on expert technical knowledge as per industry standard.

$$X_{ij} = \alpha_{ij} * w_j \quad \dots \dots \dots (4.3.1)$$

$$w_j = \frac{w_j}{\sum_{j=1}^N w_j} \quad \dots \dots \dots (4.3.2)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^N w_j = 1 \quad \dots \dots \dots (4.3.3)$$

(Assign the weight to each component characteristics and normalize, so that these sum up to 1. After that, multiply each normalized metric from step 2 by respective normalized weight.)

4. Find out PIS and NIS alternative for each criterion:

$$X_j^b = \max_{i=1}^M X_{ij} \quad \dots \dots \dots (4.4.1)$$

$$X_j^w = \min_{i=1}^M X_{ij} \quad \dots \dots \dots (4.4.2)$$

(To derive highest, lowest value of each characteristic every Component)

5. Calculate the Euclidean distance from PIS and NIS of each alternative:

$$d_i^b = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^N (X_{ij} - X_j^b)^2} \quad \dots \dots \dots (4.5.1)$$

$$d_i^w = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^N (X_{ij} - X_j^w)^2} \quad \dots \dots \dots (4.5.2)$$

(Find geometric distance between the value of each Component Characteristics for a given Component **i** and the best and worst value of such a Characteristics every Component)

6. Derive Relative Closeness to the Ideal Solution: The Outcomes of TOPSIS scores.

$$S_i = \frac{d_i^w}{d_i^w + d_i^b} \quad \dots \dots \dots (4.6.1)$$

(We derive the score for each Component that is depends on distances obtained in a step before.)

7. Ranking of Preference Order: As per the TOPSIS score by descending order.

(The Component with rank closest to the best and obtain the highest rating, therefore will be at the top most of ranking.)

V. COMPONENT SELECTION & PRIORITIZATION USING TOPSIS

The analytical research is conducted for component selection from the Commercial of the Shelf (COTS). Selection of suitable component is a complex task and plays a vital role in success of final system. It depends on multiple evaluation criteria's because criteria's may be conflict and close each other. The TOPSIS proposed to tackle such critical component selection problem. Selection can be based on multiple characteristics such as Functionality, Interoperability, Usability, Cost and other criteria's . These characteristics ranked or assessed with eminent human perspective of each component from 0 to 9 i.e(low to high).

The analytical study focused on proper selection based on its characteristics and features. The weighted significance is more or less in between multiple components. TOPSIS method implemented for component selection problem. Here the set of components as alternatives) such as i.e Comp-1, Comp-2, Comp-3, Comp-4 and Comp-5 and the set of evaluation component characteristics as criteria's such as Functionality, Usability, Interpretability and cost as given.

1. Construct decision matrix (Evaluation matrix) consisting of 5 alternatives and 4 criteria

TABLE-I. DECISION MATRIX

	Functionality	Usability	Interoperability	Cost
Comp-1	5	6	8	4
Comp-2	7	5	7	6
Comp-3	8	7	5	4
Comp-4	6	9	6	8
Comp-5	9	7	8	9
$\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}^2$	255	240	238	213
$\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}^2}$	15.9687	15.4919	15.4272	14.5945

2. Calculation of Normalized decision matrix (NDM):

TABLE – II. NORMALISED DECISION MATIRX

	Functionality	Usability	Interoperability	Cost
Comp-1	0.3131	0.3873	0.5186	0.2741
Comp-2	0.4384	0.3227	0.4537	0.4111
Comp-3	0.5010	0.4518	0.3241	0.2741
Comp-4	0.3757	0.5809	0.3889	0.5482
Comp-5	0.5636	0.4518	0.5186	0.6167

3. Determination of the Weighted Normalized Decision Matrix[WNDM] .

The weights assigned based on the expert knowledge for criteria's are given in the matrix. It is highlighted that each criterion its own weight the sum of weights equal to 1.

TABLE – III. WEIGHTED DECISION MATRIX

	Functionality	Usability	Interoperability	Cost
Weights	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Comp-1	0.0783	0.0968	0.1296	0.0685
Comp-2	0.1096	0.0807	0.1134	0.1028
Comp-3	0.1252	0.1130	0.0810	0.0685
Comp-4	0.0939	0.1452	0.0972	0.1370
Comp-5	0.1409	0.1130	0.1296	0.1542

4. Determine PIS and NIS alternative for each criterion:

TABLE –IV. POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE IDEAL SOLUTIONS

	Functionality	Usability	Interoperability	Cost
PIS(+)	0.1409	0.1452	0.1296	0.1542
NIS(-)	0.0783	0.0807	0.0810	0.0685

5. Calculate Euclidean distance from PIS and NIS of each alternative:

TABLE –V. EUCLIDEAN DISTANCE

	Euclidean Distance	
	PIS(+)	NIS(-)
Comp-1	0.1166	0.0512
Comp-2	0.0897	0.0566
Comp-3	0.1048	0.0570
Comp-4	0.0596	0.0968
Comp-5	0.0323	0.1211

6. Find the Relative Closeness to the Ideal Solution. The Outcomes are TOPSIS scores is as follows

TABLE – VI. RELATIVE CLOSENESS TO IDEAL SOLUTION

	Relative Closeness to the Ideal Solution	Rank
Comp-1	0.3052	5
Comp-2	0.3868	3
Comp-3	0.3522	4
Comp-4	0.6190	2
Comp-5	0.7896	1

Then, the Component Selection is based on relative closeness to ideal solution derived in Table-VI that can be shown in graphical representation in Fig-2.

Fig. 2: Component Selection priority

Finally, the decision matrix of final priorities denoted with TOPIS and results are mentioned in the above table. The result Component-5 is an optimum component with required features that can satisfy the stakeholder requirements and develop the robust software product.

VI. CONCLUSION

The software product quality is main objective of software engineering. The Selection of proper component from the Commercial of the Shelf(COTS) plays vital role in the Component Based Software Development. The TOPIS is an effective Multi Criteria Decision Making Quantitative Method for selecting and prioritizing the components as per the stakeholder criteria. It can solve complex problems in effective manner and satisfy the user needs in different perspectives. The author suggests that, some of the alternatives close to each other. The decision maker needs to be very cautious in assessing the inputs at decision table. This problem may occurs with logical nature of the software. The research in this area is valuable and critical and may never end. Even though, there is a extensive research is needed in the area of component selection and prioritization.

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